

UPPER SECONDARY EDUCATION CURRICULUM GUIDELINES AND THE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHING: A DISCUSSION FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF SPECIAL EDUCATION

DIRECTRICES CURRICULARES DE LA EDUCACIÓN SECUNDARIA Y LA ENSEÑANZA DE LA EDUCACIÓN FÍSICA: UNA DISCUSIÓN DESDE LA PERSPECTIVA DE LA EDUCACIÓN ESPECIAL

DIRETRIZES CURRICULARES DO ENSINO MÉDIO E O ENSINO DA EDUCAÇÃO FÍSICA: UMA DISCUSSÃO NA PERSPECTIVA DA EDUCAÇÃO ESPECIAL

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Abstract

This article aimed to analyze the curricular organizers of the Physical Education component within the Bahia Reference Curriculum Document (DCRB) for Secondary Education and their implications for the inclusion of students with disabilities. The study is characterized as qualitative documentary research. Stephen Ball's policy cycle approach was adopted—specifically the context of text production—to analyze and discuss the curricular organizers of the educational policy for Secondary Education in the State of Bahia. The findings indicate that the DCRB provides limited guidance for the promotion of inclusive pedagogical practices aimed at students with disabilities. With specific regard to the Physical Education curricular component, few references or guidelines related to Special Education were identified. Although an axis focused on adapted Physical Education is included in the second year of Secondary Education, the reinstatement of Physical Education teaching hours within the full-time curriculum matrix highlights the need to assess how this expansion will affect the teaching and learning process, particularly with respect to the effectiveness of inclusive pedagogical practices.

Keywords: Special Education; Physical Education; Curricular Policies.

Resumen

Este artículo tuvo como objetivo analizar los organizadores curriculares del Documento Curricular de Referencia de Bahía (DCRB), Educación Secundaria, del componente de Educación Física y sus implicaciones para la inclusión de estudiantes con discapacidad. La investigación se caracteriza por ser cualitativa, de tipo documental. Se utilizó el enfoque del ciclo de políticas de Stephen Ball, específicamente el contexto de producción de textos, para el análisis y discusión de los organizadores curriculares de la política educativa del Estado de Bahía para la educación

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secundaria. Se encontró que la DCRB presenta pocos lineamientos para promover prácticas pedagógicas inclusivas para estudiantes con discapacidad. Con respecto específicamente al componente curricular de Educación Física, también hubo pocas citas o lineamientos sobre educación especial. En segundo año de secundaria, sin embargo, se incluyó un eje de educación física adaptada. Se observa también que, con la reanudación de la carga horaria, para la educación de tiempo completo, de Educación Física en la matriz curricular, se hace necesario evaluar cómo esa ganancia influirá en el proceso de enseñanza y aprendizaje, especialmente en lo que respecta a la efectividad de las prácticas pedagógicas inclusivas.

Palabras clave: Educación Inclusiva; Educación física; Políticas Curriculares.

Resumo

O presente artigo teve como objetivo analisar os organizadores curriculares do Documento Curricular Referencial da Bahia (DCRB), Ensino Médio, componente Educação Física e suas implicações para a inclusão dos estudantes com deficiência. A pesquisa caracteriza-se como qualitativa, do tipo documental. Foi utilizada a abordagem do ciclo de políticas, de Stephen Ball, em específico o contexto da produção de texto, para análise e discussão dos organizadores curriculares da política educacional do ensino médio. Verificou-se que o DCRB, apresenta poucas orientações para promover uma prática pedagógica inclusiva para os alunos com deficiência. No que se refere especificamente ao componente curricular Educação Física, observou-se de igual forma poucas citações ou orientações à educação especial. No segundo ano do ensino médio, no entanto, foi incluído um eixo para Educação Física adaptada. Observa-se também a retomada da carga horária da Educação Física, com a adoção da educação em tempo integral, na matriz curricular o que torna necessário avaliar como esse ganho influenciará o processo de ensino e aprendizagem, especialmente no que diz respeito à efetividade das práticas pedagógicas inclusivas.

Palavras-chave: Educação Inclusiva; Educação Física; Políticas Curriculares.

Introduction

Discussions regarding the production and implications of official curriculum guidelines are essential for a deeper understanding of public education policies, as well as for enabling the evaluation of actions implemented in school contexts. Within this framework, the National Common Curriculum Base (BNCC) can be characterized as a normative document that establishes expectations and guidelines for the students in the Brazilian basic education. The BNCC emphasizes that all students should have access to quality education in an equitable and inclusive manner (Brasil, 2018).

Regarding educational policies, Franco and Munford (2018, p. 158) argue that “we must not disregard perspectives and constructs from the fields of public education policy and curriculum studies”, as there is a high risk that sociopolitical interests may bias conceptions of the learner, the educator, the school, as well as possibilities for curricular reform.

Beyond the federal guiding document, Brazilian states also develop their own normative curricular documents. In this context, the Bahia State Department of Education published, in 2020, the Bahia Reference Curriculum Document (DCRB) for early childhood and primary education levels. Subsequently, in 2022, the DCRB for upper secondary education and other educational modalities was released. It is important to emphasize that the DCRB, in alignment with the BNCC, advocates a curricular proposal that addresses students' needs by considering different socioeconomic conditions, race, ethnicity, religion, place of residence, and/or disability status (Bahia, 2022).

The guidelines presented in the DCRB are also consistent with the provisions of Article 206 of the Brazilian Federal Constitution, which establishes the principles of education and reaffirms the State's commitment to promoting, among other conditions, equal conditions for access to and permanence in school; freedom to learn, teach, research, and disseminate thought, art, and knowledge; and the provision of free public education in official institutions (Brasil, 1988). These principles underscore the need to guarantee inclusive education that promotes, above all, learning as a fundamental right of all students.

Therefore, education should not be understood merely as access to enrollment, but rather as encompassing multiple dimensions, including the provision of resources and services and the development of methodological strategies that consider individual needs, thereby enabling students' permanence and continuity in academic life, especially for students with disabilities, and contributing to ensuring that all guaranteed rights are effectively accessible to them.

Physical Education, as a curricular component within the area of Languages, provides learning experiences that foster students' holistic and critical development, taking into account their differences and specificities, particularly those of students with disabilities. Nevertheless, significant challenges remain in relation to the inclusion of students with specific educational needs in Physical Education classes. A recent bibliographic study examining Brazilian research published between 2008 and 2018 in the journals *Movimento*, *Revista Brasileira de Ciências do Esporte*, and *Pensar a Prática* found that teachers continue to express a sense of pessimism regarding the inclusion process in

school contexts, largely attributed to insufficient training, limited support for curricular planning, and inadequate physical infrastructure to promote a more inclusive school environment (Garozzi; Chicon; Sá, 2021).

Considering the context presented, this study aims to analyze the curricular organizers of the DCRB for Upper Secondary Education, specifically within the Physical Education component, and their implications for the inclusion of students with disabilities. Accordingly, the research sought to answer the following questions: How is the concept of inclusion of students with disabilities addressed in the document? And do the curricular organizers of the area of Languages—particularly those related to the Physical Education component in Upper Secondary Education as presented in the DCRB—provide support for the learning process of students with disabilities?

Inclusive education encompasses policies that establish rights and guidelines to ensure access to and permanence within the school environment, as well as the full development of students' abilities and the realization of their potential. This commitment entails guaranteeing conditions for meaningful learning and access to historically produced cultural and sociocultural assets. A recent bibliographic survey (Bruzaca et al., 2024), highlights both advances and persistent challenges in areas related to the rights, educational processes, and literacy of students with disabilities. However, the analysis of specific curricular components remains underexplored in the literature. This gap underscores the need for studies that examine normative and curricular documents in greater depth, in order to identify weaknesses, inconsistencies, and silences, thereby contributing to the improvement of guidelines and the development of more effective approaches in the field of inclusive education.

Scientific evidence on the benefits of physical exercise and Physical Education in school settings for children and adolescents is well established in the literature. Such benefits extend beyond cognitive, motor, and psychosocial gains to include significant effects on learning processes, self-regulation, subjective well-being, and the development of social bonds. This body of evidence has supported international recommendations for the systematic inclusion of physical activity in school contexts (World Health Organization, 2020).

However, although these benefits are widely recognized, recent studies indicate that the implementation of truly inclusive Physical Education still faces structural, pedagogical, and curricular challenges, particularly with regard to adapting practices to the specific needs of students with disabilities (Borland et al., 2022; Gámez-Calvo et al., 2024; Tarantino, Makopoulou, & Neville, 2022). This mismatch between the acknowledged potential of Physical Education and the concrete conditions of its implementation in everyday school practice, reveals a significant gap in both scientific production and educational policies. It also underscores the importance of studies that critically examine curricular documents and normative guidelines, in order to contribute to the advancement of academic debate, the improvement of pedagogical practices, and the expansion of the right to education for all students.

In light of the discussion presented thus far and in pursuit of the study's objective, this research draws on the work of the British scholar Stephen Ball and his collaborators, who developed the policy cycle approach as a framework for analyzing educational policies. This approach seeks to understand how policies are formulated, what their objectives are, and how they are enacted in the everyday life of schools. It comprises three main contexts: the context of influence, the context of text production, and the context of practice, which are interconnected yet can be examined analytically as distinct dimensions (Souza et al., 2022).

Methodology

This study is characterized as qualitative research. According to this approach, Ludke and André (1986) argue that qualitative research is marked by the investigation of phenomena in their natural settings, the direct involvement of the researcher with the object of study, and data collection processes that focus on non-metric variables.

The qualitative approach enables a deeper and more detailed analysis of the object of study, while also offering a set of procedures that support the construction of qualitative data.

For the development and collection of the data analyzed in this study, document analysis procedures were adopted. Document analysis is a methodological procedure that

employs techniques for the examination, interpretation, and analysis of documents of various types, with the purpose of extracting thematic or lexical meanings (Sá-Silva; Almeida; Guindani, 2009).

The primary source of analysis was the Bahia Reference Curriculum Document – Upper Secondary Education Stage (Bahia, 2022), which is a publicly available document. In line with Sá-Silva, Almeida, and Guindani (2009), we acknowledge that the analysis of policy documents is not a simple task; rather, it is a highly complex process that requires researchers to be capable of identifying ideologies, interests, employed concepts, debates involved in the process, as well as voices that are both present and absent, among other aspects.

Initially, a preliminary assessment of the document was conducted. Subsequently, priority was given to the sections addressing the area of Languages and their technologies, as well as the Physical Education curricular component.

After the organization, grouping, and comprehension of the data, content analysis procedures were adopted. Content analysis is understood as a set of techniques that enable the analysis of communications and the interpretation of the knowledge contained in messages. This technique comprises different phases of analysis, organized around three chronological stages: (a) pre-analysis; (b) exploration of the material; and (c) treatment of results, inference, and interpretation (Bardin, 1977).

With regard to the theoretical and methodological frameworks, it is important to emphasize the need to broaden the dialogue between the fields of Educational Policy and inclusive education, given the context of significant theoretical and practical complexities. In this sense, the policy cycle approach enables a critical discussion of the trajectory of educational policies by considering different stages, ranging from their initial formulation to their implementation (Mainardes, 2006). In this article, the theoretical assumptions of the policy cycle were adopted, with particular attention to the context of text production. This perspective makes it possible to understand the disputes, agreements, and consensuses among groups occupying different positions in the formulation of policy texts (Corrêa, 2018).

Finally, the data were organized into two categories of analysis: (a) Bahia's curricular guidelines and their approach to inclusion; and (b) the approach presented in the documents regarding Physical Education for students with disabilities: is inclusion possible?

Results and Discussion

Bahia's Curriculum Guidelines and the Approach to the Inclusion of Students with Disabilities

The document analysis conducted in this study examined the final version of the Bahia Reference Curriculum Document for Upper Secondary Education (Bahia, 2022). The document presents a proposed curricular organization for different educational modalities, including Part-Time Upper Secondary Education, Full-Time Upper Secondary Education, Technological Mediation (EMITec), Vocational Education, Technological Education, and Night Education. In addition, it provides guidelines for Indigenous School Education, Quilombola School Education, Rural Education, Special Education, and Education for Young People, Adults, and Older Adults (EJAI).

It is worth noting that the DCRB is composed of 18 sections, totaling 576 pages. Its structure includes a brief presentation, an introduction, and the legal frameworks that underpin the document. This is followed by the presentation of its guiding principles, structuring axes, and conceptual foundations. The text also addresses the challenges of upper secondary education in the state of Bahia, including a discussion of the profile of students enrolled in the public education system. Subsequently, the document presents the curricular matrices and the curricular organizers organized by areas of knowledge (Bahia, 2022).

Overall, the final version of the document shows a limited incidence of direct references to the education of students with disabilities. The term "*inclusion of people with disabilities*" appears only once throughout the text, while the expression "*people with disabilities*" is used eight times, predominantly in normative and declarative passages. In addition, occurrences of the terms "*persons with disabilities*" (three times) and "*students with disabilities*" (once) were identified, the former being conceptually outdated and inconsistent with the terminology consolidated in current Brazilian legislation.

The qualitative analysis of the terminology reveals that such references occur predominantly in a generic manner, largely restricted to the reaffirmation of legal principles, without being translated into concrete pedagogical, curricular, or didactic-methodological guidelines, particularly in the field of Physical Education. This discursive

pattern indicates not only a low level of conceptual density regarding inclusive education within the document, but also a structuring silence concerning Special Education as a specific pedagogical field. This finding corroborates critiques identified in analyses of the BNCC, which point to the fragility of incorporating inclusion into official curricular texts and to the gap between normative discourse and the concrete conditions for organizing pedagogical work (Ferreira; Moreira; Volsi, 2020). Furthermore, the occurrence and detailed analysis of these terms are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Occurrence and Qualitative Analysis of Terms Related to Special Education in the DCRB (Secondary Education), 2022.

Term identified	N° of occurrences	DCRB Page	Representative Excerpt	Critical Analysis
"Inclusion of people with disabilities"	01	p. 29;	"Establishes the Brazilian Law for the Inclusion of Persons with Disabilities."	Generic formulation, normative statement.
"people with disabilities"	08	p. 29; 40; 42; 77;77; 287; 298; 413;	"It is known that there is specific legislation that caters to people with disabilities, and the school and the State cannot fail to meet the specific needs of these individuals."	Legal references predominate, associated with the description of the students' profile, and appear as content of the Educational Itinerary in the area of human sciences.
"Persons with disabilities"	03	p. 18; 265; 281;	"Detailed analysis of technological contributions to neurodegenerative diseases and a survey of assistive technologies for persons with disabilities."	Use of a term superseded by legislation (LBI). Indicates a lack of updated regulations and may reproduce an ableist view.
"students with disabilities"	01	p. 28;	"...guide these modalities understanding that students with disabilities, indigenous students, quilombola students, rural students, young people and adults, in secondary education..."	Term used in a discursive/normative way.

Source: Authors.

Regarding the silencing of discussions on Special Education in official documents, Ferreira, Moreira, and Volsi draw attention to the following:

Studies have revealed a silencing of Special Education within the BNCC. There is an absence of a clear conception of Special Education, as well as of theoretical and methodological support and guidelines capable of underpinning the organization of schools' pedagogical-curricular proposals, in order to ensure the provision of Special Education from an inclusive perspective. (Ferreira; Moreira; Volsi, 2020, p. 28)

In DCRB, the concept of “*inclusion of persons with disabilities*” is used more specifically to present the norms and legislation related to the Special Education modality. This section outlines regulatory frameworks ranging from the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities of the United Nations (incorporated into the Brazilian legal framework through Resolution No. 04/2009/CNE/CEB), to the Brazilian Inclusion Law (Law No. 13.146 of July 6, 2015), as well as the Inclusive Education Guidelines of the State of Bahia (Cruz; Andrade, 2017).

Since the enactment of the Brazilian Inclusion Law in 2015, there has been a clear normative consolidation regarding the need to promote and ensure the rights of persons with disabilities, representing a significant legal milestone for Special Education. The law reaffirms rights related to accessibility, education, the removal of barriers, and access to assistive technologies, among others (Brazil, 2015). When specifically addressing the right to education, the legislation emphasizes the need for an inclusive education system that guarantees the permanence and development of students with disabilities within school settings. It also highlights the importance of coordinated action among educational institutions, education professionals, and public authorities in the development of actions, resources, and services aimed at expanding these students’ learning potential.

With regard to the Inclusive Education Guidelines referenced in the DCRB, these aim to guide pedagogical action directed toward students with disabilities, as well as students with pervasive developmental disorders and those with high abilities/giftedness, across different educational settings. However, as Cruz and Andrade (2017, p. 43) point out, “the practice produced in mainstream schools emerges as the greatest challenge to the viability of this proposal, since it is in this space that the most significant forms of discrimination occur.” Although the guidelines offer important orientations for the implementation of a more inclusive education, they do not clearly articulate the means necessary for the effective realization of the rights of students within Special Education, and they acknowledge the challenges involved in implementing pedagogical practices in mainstream classrooms.

In this regard, it is important to highlight that, although the Bahia Reference Curriculum Document (DCRB) presents norms and legislation emphasizing the importance of a curricular proposal that addresses the needs of students with disabilities—stating that schools and the State cannot “fail to meet the specific needs of these individuals” (Bahia,

2022, p. 77)—the document does not explicitly specify how curricula should be developed to ensure a more inclusive education. The inconsistencies observed in the official text reveal weaknesses in the logical organization of the writing, a lack of clarity, and significant conflicts and contradictions within public policy documents (Ball, 1994).

It is also important to emphasize the need to provide clear guidelines and theoretical-methodological support to ensure both the permanence of students with disabilities in school and the quality of pedagogical support offered to them. Although legislation guarantees the access of persons with disabilities to mainstream education systems, numerous barriers persist in practice that hinder the effective realization of inclusion. These barriers include insufficient training for teachers and school staff, the lack of curricular guidance for the implementation of effective pedagogical proposals, and inadequate physical infrastructure (Melero, 2013).

In sum, it is essential to recognize that the absence and/or superficial treatment of discussions on Special Education in the DCRB, as well as the contradictions identified in the aforementioned secondary documents, cannot be analyzed in a static, superficial, or linear manner. It is necessary to consider the different contexts and actors involved in the formulation, interpretation³, translation⁴, and recontextualization of policies, as well as the ongoing power relations and competing interests that shape whether policy texts are effectively translated into practice (Mainardes, 2018).

Considering the policy cycle approach—particularly the context of text production—the DCRB can be understood as a policy text resulting from disputes, negotiations, and consensuses among different groups, in which certain agendas gain centrality while others are marginalized or silenced (Mainardes, 2006; Corrêa, 2018). From this perspective, although the document formally acknowledges the presence of students with disabilities in upper secondary education, this recognition functions primarily as an organizational reference rather than as a pedagogical-curricular guideline capable of orienting teaching practice.

³ In the policy cycle approach, interpretation is a theoretical perspective that seeks to understand policy. (Mainardes, 2018)

⁴ And translation is a creative and productive resource that involves developing strategies to put a policy into action. (Mainardes, 2018).

Furthermore, the theme is addressed in a predominantly normative and declaratory manner, with low guiding density. The very expression associated with inclusion appears primarily linked to a list of legal frameworks (for example, the title of the Brazilian Inclusion Law), without theoretical-methodological or didactic-evaluative developments that clarify how participation and learning are to be ensured within the curriculum in action. From the perspective of the policy cycle, this suggests that the text affirms inclusion as a principle but fails to translate it into consistent curricular operators (Mainardes, 2006).

It is important to recognize that policies are interpreted and enacted in different ways. Accordingly, the actors involved—in this case, students, parents, teachers, coordinators, and administrators—need not act as mere spectators; rather, they can expose and challenge the contradictions present in official normative texts (De Sousa, 2018). Such engagement fosters debate and creates conditions for official documents, legislation, ordinances, and policy publications to be reviewed, refined, and effectively implemented in practice.

Curricular Organizers for Physical Education and Students with Disabilities: Is Inclusion Possible?

The analysis of the Bahia Reference Curriculum Document (DCRB) for Upper Secondary Education—specifically focusing on the area of Languages and their technologies and on the Physical Education curricular component—maintains the approach previously identified in relation to Special Education, characterized by general and superficial references. Consequently, the document does not propose clearly defined guidelines or directions regarding pedagogical approaches for this area, nor for the specific curricular component, with respect to working with students with disabilities. Although the document presents few concrete proposals for the education of these students, it reiterates the need to guarantee their rights, highlighting this as one of the challenges faced by schools, in addition to referencing learning objectives and the skills and competencies to be developed in order to promote inclusion.

It is important to highlight that the area of Languages—comprising Portuguese Language, Mother Tongue (for Indigenous populations), Modern Foreign Language, Art, and Physical Education—is grounded in the appropriation and experimentation of diverse

communicative processes. This framework enables students to access knowledge of artistic, bodily, and verbal languages in their different manifestations, thereby contributing to the exercise of citizenship and to the promotion of students' cultural development within the Bahia public education system (Bahia, 2022).

With specific regard to the Physical Education curricular component, the document acknowledges that it should be offered in a manner that reaches all students, regardless of their specific needs. It states that “this component should be offered to all ‘Upper Secondary Education students’ and taught by teachers holding a degree in Physical Education” (Bahia, 2022, p. 96).

When presenting language-related skills linked to competencies, the DCRB acknowledges the need to democratize access to the body culture of movement, guiding practices to take into account diversity among individuals and to promote social interactions grounded in respect for differences. In this sense, it anticipates the development of skills that “use body movements consciously and intentionally to interact socially in body culture practices, in order to establish constructive and ethical relationships that respect differences” (Bahia, 2022, p. 107).

When addressing the objects of knowledge in Physical Education, the Bahia Reference Curriculum Document (DCRB) specifically identifies a section dedicated to sports, with an emphasis on adapted sports, in the second year of Upper Secondary Education (Bahia, 2022). Although limited in scope and lacking in detail, this inclusion represents a specific articulation with the field of inclusive Physical Education and Paralympic sport, signaling a discursive advance in the recognition of the theme within the prescribed curriculum. However, from the perspective of the policy cycle, it is necessary to understand that the curricular document, as a policy text, expresses choices, disputes, and partial compromises, simultaneously encompassing both possibilities and limitations (Mainardes, 2006). Thus, the presence of “adapted sports” in the text does not, in itself, guarantee its effectiveness in the context of practice. The absence of explicit theoretical-methodological frameworks, didactic guidelines, and evaluative criteria tends to shift responsibility to teachers for translating this directive into pedagogical action, which may exacerbate asymmetries in implementation and hinder the consolidation of consistent inclusive practices.

Although the recent curricular reorganization (Bahia, 2025) has reinstated the workload of the Physical Education component in the Bahia Reference Curriculum Document (DCRB), for Upper Secondary Education—re-establishing two weekly classes throughout the cycle in full-time education—, there remains a need for a deeper understanding of how this change affects the organization of teaching work, particularly in light of the demands related to planning, assessment, and adaptation for students with disabilities. Furthermore, it is necessary to examine how the increased workload will influence the teaching and learning process, especially with regard to the effectiveness of inclusive pedagogical practices.

It should also be considered that recommendations advocate for students with disabilities to have access to the common curriculum, so that all students may achieve the objectives of education. However, it is essential that curricular flexibility be ensured in order to adequately address the specific needs of these students (Cruz; Andrade, 2017).

In this sense, Cruz and Andrade (2018, p. 45) further argue that:

Special and inclusive education is conceived as a means of enabling all students to achieve the objectives of general education, employing differentiated teaching and learning processes when necessary, without depriving them of access to curricular subjects and their respective programmatic contents.

Considering this context, for the content prescribed in the Bahia Reference Curriculum Document (DCRB) for the Physical Education component to effectively reach students with disabilities, adaptations that take into account the diverse conditions presented by them are required. In this respect, inclusion is realized through addressing students' specific needs, as well as through adaptations in lesson structure, teacher mediation, and the expansion and diversification of practices that provide opportunities for meaningful experiences and knowledge of the various elements of body culture.

In addition to ensuring greater democratization of Physical Education content for students within Special Education, it is necessary to consider important behavioral factors that contribute to a more inclusive context. These include more effective teacher communication, which should involve the provision of diverse stimuli—physical, verbal, and gestural—in order to facilitate and enhance understanding among all students. Furthermore, when necessary, teachers should adapt rules, materials, space, and instructional methodologies to ensure participation, particularly for students with disabilities (Carvalho; Araújo, 2018).

Beyond the need for clearer guidance in official curricular documents addressing Special Education, it remains essential to examine the effective implementation of curricular proposals in teaching practice. Such guidelines must also indicate curricular adaptations capable of offering appropriate educational responses to students' needs and of enhancing learning opportunities. Moreover, another critical issue for effective implementation—and, consequently, for the development of more inclusive proposals in schools—concerns teacher education and training (Pimentel; Ribeiro, 2021). This is because professional training programs may fail to provide the theoretical and practical foundations necessary for teachers to engage in inclusive teaching practices (Martins et al., 2019).

In light of the foregoing, the complex and controversial nature of educational policies aimed at inclusive education—particularly within the Physical Education curricular component—is reinforced. In the case of the DCRB, notable weaknesses are evident in the treatment of this issue, marked by the absence of an intentional and systematized articulation capable of providing teachers and the broader school community with theoretical-methodological and didactic-pedagogical support for the effective inclusion of students with disabilities in Physical Education classes.

In this sense, achieving inclusion requires the consideration of integrated actions, such as: collaborative pedagogical planning among Physical Education teachers, the school management team, Specialized Educational Assistance professionals, and other teachers, with the definition of shared objectives and participation strategies; curricular and methodological adaptations focused on functionality and learning, involving adjustments to rules, materials, space, time, and forms of activity organization, without reducing pedagogical demands; the adoption of teaching strategies that broaden participation, including tasks graded by levels of complexity, multiple forms of engagement and demonstration of learning, clear instructions, and visual and tactile resources; and inclusive and formative assessment practices, with explicit criteria, continuous monitoring of individual progress, and recognition of diverse forms of performance, while also taking into account class size and the need for increased planning time.

Finally, ensuring ongoing teacher education and institutional support—articulating the foundations of inclusive Physical Education, Paralympic sport, and evidence-based practices—is essential. These measures shift inclusion from a merely declarative stance to

a curriculum in action, strengthening the rights to participation, learning, and a sense of belonging in school for students with disabilities.

Therefore, it is necessary to advance strategies aimed at consolidating a more inclusive Physical Education. Moreover, it is essential to expand studies and discussions within the context of practice in order to identify teachers' interpretations and translations of specific Special Education legislation, since "the actions of social actors" are fundamental to understanding public policies (Mainardes; Ferreira; Tello, 2011). This is because it is within the context of practice that policies can be recreated and resignified (Ball, 2001).

Final considerations

This article allows us to conclude that the published version of the Bahia Reference Curriculum Document (DCRB) for Upper Secondary Education, as an educational policy proposal that standardizes and guides the construction of school curricula, provides limited guidance for the promotion of inclusive pedagogical practices for students with disabilities. Discussions related to Special Education are addressed in a punctual and superficial manner throughout the document. With regard to the Physical Education curricular component, the inclusion of a sports axis with an emphasis on adapted sports in the second year of Upper Secondary Education was identified. Although this represents a relevant advance, it still lacks further development regarding the specific modalities to be addressed, as well as the expansion of such content to other grades within Upper Secondary Education. Moreover, the guidelines presented in the document remain insufficient to ensure the construction of an inclusive curriculum, particularly within the Physical Education curricular component.

Further studies are needed to advance strategies aimed at consolidating a more inclusive Physical Education, as well as to deepen the understanding of the context of practice, in order to identify how teachers interpret and translate specific Special Education legislation.

In conclusion, the absence of clear and systematic guidelines for Physical Education practice aimed at students with specific needs represents a significant challenge to the effective implementation of quality inclusive education. The lack of such guidance limits the adaptation of pedagogical practices to the physical, cognitive, and emotional demands

of these students, thereby restricting their full participation in school activities and the development of essential skills. Furthermore, the limited availability of continuing professional development for Physical Education teachers—who are often insufficiently prepared to address this diversity—contributes to the persistence of barriers to inclusion. Advancing in this context requires the establishment of more public policies that are inclusive and pedagogical strategies, as well as the expansion of teacher education initiatives, ensuring more sensitive responses to students' needs and fostering a more equitable and accessible school environment. In this way, it becomes possible to build a more inclusive educational landscape that promotes equal opportunities for all students and supports both human and social development.

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